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Translating research ethics and integrity to society through the work of science communication

Irene Monsonís-Payá¹ and Richard Woolley²

¹irmonpa@doctor.upv.es

[0000-0001-7140-6209](tel:0000-0001-7140-6209)

INGENIO (CSIC-UPV), Universitat Politècnica de València, Valencia, Spain

²ricwoo@upv.edu.es

[0000-0003-1247-8776](tel:0000-0003-1247-8776)

INGENIO (CSIC-UPV), Universitat Politècnica de València, Valencia, Spain

Abstract

The communication of science is crucial to public trust in science. This paper reports work-in-progress on a study of science communicators' work and how scientific information and results are translated to citizens. We examine how research ethics and integrity (REI) work practices and institutional processes are understood and translated by science communicators. Our provisional results show that formal institutional processes are not important in communicators' work, which depends more on their social embeddedness in interpersonal relationships, their experience and understanding of the construction of the frontier of a scientific field - and key processes such as peer review and publishing - to perform assessments of the credibility of the information they use as inputs to their work. The translation of REI to the public is thus more dependent on interpretive and creative processes of science communicators' work than it is on formal markers of REI in knowledge production.

1. Introduction: public trust in science

Public trust in science is an object of sustained interest in European research and innovation (R&I) policy. Scholarly understanding of public trust has moved through a series of explanations, from the 'deficit' model of public understanding to approaches considering a greater complexity in science-society relations (Bauer et al., 2007; Hu, 2024). An initial paradigm appeared in the 1960s, based on the premise that populations need to attain a certain degree of "science literacy" to enable citizens to participate in political life in an appropriate manner (Bauer et al., 2007). The concept of science literacy refers to knowledge of facts of science, and understanding of its methodologies and of the positive outcomes of science and technology (Miller, 1983, 1998). Under this paradigm, education is the key strategy to overcome the 'public deficit' of scientific knowledge. Population surveys have been developed as instruments designed to measure the level of scientific literacy in a target population (Miller, 1983).

A second paradigm gained prominence with the publication of 'The Public Understanding of Science', also known as the 'Bodmer report' by the Royal Society (1985). The focus moved from measuring and trying to improve the level of scientific knowledge of the population to understanding the correlation between scientific literacy and public attitudes towards science (Durant et al., 2000). Responding in part to supposed public suspicion of science in the wake of cases such as Mad Cow Disease, this paradigm shift centres on securing citizen support for science and its public funding, rather than on a purely democratic participation imperative (Wynne, 1992). The public understanding of science paradigm (PUS) was promoted using the

axiom ‘the more you know, the more you love it’ (Bauer et al., 2007). Hu (2024: 713) summarised the core assumptions of PUS:

- (1) science plays an unquestionably essential and (and positive) role in improving our personal life and social prosperity, (2) there is a deficit in the understanding of science among the public, (3) scientist have the authority and obligation to reduce this lack of knowledge through one-direction transmission, and (4) public interest in and support of science are related to their knowledge about science.

Following 15 years of PUS promotion in the UK, including the creation of the dedicated Committee of Public Understanding on Science (CoPUS), empirical studies failed to show conclusive evidence of a positive relationship between public knowledge about science and positive attitudes toward it, but “a more reflexive approach to public understanding of science was developing” (Miller, 2001). The evolution in the PUS paradigm was marked by the publication of the ‘Science and Society’ report of the UK House of Lords (2020) and can be characterised as based around an interactive and co-productive understanding of science – society relationships (Miller, 2001).

The science and society approach shifts focus from increasing science literacy towards increasing citizens’ involvement in scientific and technological issues (Horst, 2008). This model invokes a new configuration of ‘deficit’, this time in relation to failures of scientific and technological institutions and experts to meaningfully and effectively engage with citizens and lay-persons (Bauer et al., 2007). Also labelled as the “deliberation Model” (Horst, 2008), “public engagement” (European Commission, 2014; Hu, 2024) and “science with and for society” (European Commission, 2014; Randles et al., 2016), the transformed core assumptions of this paradigm were summarised by Hu (2024: 715):

- (1) scientific knowledge is not self-evidently unproblematic, but subject to intrinsic uncertainties and risks; (2) publics have valuable understanding and expertise in technoscientific issues; (3) their insights should be fully considered in the decisions on scientific development and applications; and (4) once publics are fully engaged in such processes, science and technology can proceed in a responsible, acceptable, and prosperous manner.

Public participation in, and deliberation on, science, innovation and technology issues become understood as integral to the development of a strategic approach to improving ‘public trust in science’, including designing tools and mechanisms to better involve citizens in scientific work (Bernstein et al., 2022). The increasing importance of ‘values’ in the contested terrains of ‘post-normal’ science (Funtowicz & Ravetz, 1993) has been exacerbated by the framing of R&I in the eyes of citizens as essential to the combatting of global challenges such as climate change (Stilgoe et al., 2013).

Evolution in models of public trust in science summarised here run alongside empirical studies that have pointed to the existence of periods of public disaffection with science (Bauer et al., 1995). This resulted in increasing alarms about a supposed ‘crisis’ in public trust in science and social institutions (Saltelli & Funtowicz, 2017). This crisis of trust in science has had two distinct explanations. On the one hand, models of public trust in science shifted from attributing the crisis of trust from ignorance of the public to the inherent unpredictability of science (Hu, 2024). On the other hand, blame has been apportioned to the governance in science and public perceptions of inappropriate or improper conduct among scientists and within scientific

organisations. Such conduct includes the crisis of reproducibility of scientific results, egregious cases of scientific fraud and misconduct (Saltelli & Funtowicz, 2017), and questionable research practices (Martinson et al., 2005), behaviours provoked in part by inappropriate institutional incentives (Bonn & Pinxten, 2019). The carefully crafted image of science as value neutral and objective has been further shaken by the politicisation of science (Alinejad & Honari, 2024) and the use of disinformation and promotion of uncertainty about science as a socio-political weapon (Fisher, 2022).

Despite this perceived turbulence in science – society relations, studies of public perceptions of scientists continues to show high levels of trust and support for the profession (Cologna et al., 2025). Contemporary empirical studies on trust in science typically measure trustworthiness through scales combining three dimensions, capturing perception of citizen on expertise or competence, benevolence, and integrity (Besley & Tiffany, 2023; Hendriks et al., 2015). In recent studies (Cologna et al., 2025), the dimension ‘openness’ has been included to also capture perceptions of the willingness of scientists to listen, or to give others a ‘voice’ (Besley et al., 2021). Continued public trust in science has been argued to be an important contributing factor in mobilising citizens to take action to tackle climate change (Cologna & Siegrist, 2020) and to follow COVID-19 mitigation and prevention guidelines (Plohl & Musil, 2021).

2. Science communicators and their roles

The space of science communication has become increasingly complex and multidimensional, featuring a greater diversity of communicator types, channels for circulation, and multiplication of the formats of communication objects. This shift is often characterised as moving from a relatively linear transmission of information through broadcast and publishing companies, directed to relatively passive audiences, to the dialogic and interactive curating, customising, and sharing of information among institutional, commercial, and social organisations and citizens (Biermann & Taddicken, 2025; Brüggemann et al., 2020; Fahy & Nisbet, 2011). Key ‘opinion leaders’ in ‘mass media’, including specialised science journalists, continue to mediate information for the public as first characterised in the two-step model of communication (Katz & Lazarsfeld, 1955; Nisbet, 2018). However, they also now share the space of science communication with popular influencers and content creators including Youtubers, bloggers, podcasters and other specialists in digital media production (Davies, 2021). In addition, for varying reasons, institutional actors involved in scientific knowledge production have become more directly involved in science communication, including scientists, research performing organisations, universities, publishers, museums, research groups and clinical and public healthcare professionals (Intemann, 2023).

The changing dynamics of the space of science communication, driven by changes in technology and the multiplication of actors and channels that structure this space has been accompanied by changes in the goals and objectives of science communicators. According to Intemann (2023) the goals of science communication have expanded from accurate conveying of information to promote understanding, to also include ‘predictive relevance, the motivation of actions, generation of interest and the facilitation of trust. According to Davies (2021: 123), science communication becomes more important pragmatically as it “provides individuals with knowledge that the need to navigate life in contemporary, technologically saturated societies”. This communication activity takes place in a variety of definable spaces with contextual norms and values including the online arena, expert arena, mass media arena and discussion arena (Schmidt, 2013).

In a science communication space with such increasingly complex, interactive, and heterogeneous dynamics, it follows that the roles of science communicators have also changed. Social roles can include the attitudes, expectations, behaviours and values that guide individuals in certain situations when performing a specific task (Turner, 2001). Among professional occupations such as science journalists in mass media organisations, these roles can include historical, contextual, situational, plural and non-mutually exclusive sets of functions that can be competing in different ways across space and time (Mellado & Alfaro, 2020). While professional journalists often remain “the adult public’s central source of scientific information” (Funk, Gottfried and Mitchell, 2017 in Schipani, 2024: 56), the roles of science journalist are argued to have shaped, and been shaped by, the evolution of the space of science communication. Fahy and Nisbet (2011: 789) argue that “journalists have moved from their historically dominant role as privileged conveyers of scientific findings to an increasing plurality of roles that involve diverse, pluralistic and interactive ways of telling science news”. They identify an expanded typology of science journalism roles including conduit, public intellectual, agenda-setter, watchdog, investigative reporter, civic educator, curator, convenor and advocate (2011: 780). While less is known about the roles of other types of science communicators compared to science journalists the growing importance of these diverse communicators makes this an important area for future study, Nevertheless, even in such an uncertain context, it appears safe to assume that science communication outputs, with their multiple forms, channels of curation, mediation, and circulation, are part of a wider universe of ‘content creation’ that is in part ‘co-produced’ also by those actors who formerly took on the passive role of ‘audience’.

Finally, we may want to consider whether science communicators also play an emerging role as ‘crisis managers’. In general, communicators’ roles can be argued to have shifted toward “post-normal science communication” in which dealing with uncertainty, value questions, urgency to take actions and political pressures (Brüggemann et al., 2020), is integral to their work. This conceptualisation of an emergent role for science communicators of multiple types can particularly be observed in the case of climate change and COVID-19 where injunctions to ‘follow the science’ were shown to be insufficient and at times counterproductive in the communication of information in a context of science-infused public health.

This work-in-progress paper reports on research into an important dimension of science – society relationships and the construction of public trust in science. The translation of information about scientific horizons, work, and results by scientific communicators helps educate, inform and expose aspects of science to citizens through a variety of public fora. The study investigates the role of scientific communicators, including press officers, journalists, popularisers, bloggers and social media influencers, in communicating science and how this may relate to public trust in science. In particular, we are interested in whether and/or how research ethics and integrity (REI) practices in scientific work and institutions influences levels or aspects of public trust. The idea that improving research ethics and integrity could have a positive relationship with public trust in science has recently been embraced at institutional policy level, with the European Commission for example considering that “[t]rust depends on scientists and engineers’ capacity to demonstrate high standards of research integrity, and ethical mind-set, [...]” (European Commission, 2022). The study was conducted in 2024 involving participants from seven European countries, focusing also on the science communication contexts of climate change and the COVID-19 pandemic.

3. Research approach and method

The research approach for the study was published in an open research protocol ahead of the fieldwork (Monsonís-Payá & Woolley, 2024). The protocol contained sufficient detail to enable a consistent implementation of the research approach by the seven research teams collecting primary data (Denmark, France, Germany, Greece, Portugal, Spain, United Kingdom). In addition, an online training session was conducted to build a shared understanding of how to use the interview instrument and interviewer guide (Monsonís-Payá & Woolley, 2024). The study received ethics approval from the *Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas* (CSIC) Ethics Committee (approval number 300/2023). Data handling and management was governed by the project Data Management Plan and a Joint Data Controller Agreement signed by all project partners. These agreements specify permitted actions and processes regarding data security, handling, and use of the primary data generated.

The research approach was based on a conceptual heuristic guiding the study design, in which scientific institutions, citizen participation, and research ethics and integrity are considered antecedents of public trust in science. The main empirical research question asked how research ethics and integrity practices are translated to society through the work of science communicators, and whether this translation process is perceived to have an effect on citizens' trust in science. Semi-structured interviews were used to explore how information about research ethics and integrity practices in the lab is translated to different publics by science communicators.

Analysis was conducted of how 'chains of mediation' between science and society are constructed through the interlinked workflows of press officers, journalists, science writers, bloggers and other professional and citizen communicators of science. We understand these communicators as 'mediators', following the sociology of translation, as acting within socio-technical networks that transform information as it moves from one time and place to another (Latour, 2005). We also investigate these communicators' interactions with different audiences and their perspectives on the 'democratisation of science' through mechanisms such as citizen science. Interviewees were selected also on the basis of their work in the science communication contexts of the Covid-19 pandemic and Climate Change, enabling us to assess science communication practices in contexts of crisis and controversy that entangle science and society, often placing considerable stress on communicators and citizens alike.

2.1. Study participants

A total of 78 science communicators participated in the study, including 37 women and 41 men. The interviewees were selected through an information-centred sampling strategy to identify professionals and practitioners representing a range of professional and practitioner roles in science communication (Flyvbjerg, 2001). We also sought to stratify our sample by gender, career stage, and participation in the communication contexts of climate change and COVID-19. Table 1 summarises the countries and the gender, career stage and communicator type of the participants.

Table 1. Interview participants, by gender, career stage, and communicator type (n=78)

Country	Gender		Career stage			Communicator type			
	Female	Male	Early	Mid	Senior	Science writer or communicator	Journalist	Blogs, podcasts, other content	Institutional
Denmark	3	7	-	-	10	4	2	1	3
France	7	7	7	5	2	3	4	1	6
Germany	5	5	1	3	6	3	4	1	2
Greece	3	8	-	5	6	2	2	3	4
Portugal	8	3	1	4	6	1	2	6	2
Spain	3	8	1	5	5	5	1	2	3
UK	8	3	1	2	8	1	1	3	6
TOTAL	37	41	11	24	43	19	16	17	26

Table 2 summarises the main sources of information that participants use in their work. Table 3 describes the main types of communication outputs that the participants produce, while Table 4 summarises the main channels through which these outputs are put into circulation.

Table 2: Science communicators' main sources of information for their work (n=78)

Country	Interpersonal networks		Science press releases		Science literature	Main-stream media	Social media	Selected others
	<i>With researchers</i>	<i>With science communicators</i>	<i>RPOs</i>	<i>Publishers</i>				
Denmark	9	7	6	1	10	7	5	Political actors
France	13	5	5	5	4	5	7	RPO scientific leadership
Germany	10	5	6	-	10	3	3	Professional associations; Science Media Center
Greece	5	4	4	6	7	3	2	International publishers
Portugal	11	6	2	1	8	5	2	Technical manuals; documentaries & TV; Institutional committees; Clients; Websites
Spain	10	8	4	3	10	2	3	Professional associations; Legislation; Court sentencing repository; Science textbooks
UK	7	5	2	2	7	6	6	-
TOTAL	65	40	29	18	56	31	28	

Table 3: Types of communication outputs produced by science communicators (n=78)

Country	Books	Articles	TV	Radio	Podcast	Social Media			Selected others
						<i>Visual</i>	<i>Text</i>	<i>Live</i>	
Denmark	4	8	2	3	4	-	7	-	-
France	3	11	1	2	2	5	13	1	Games; graphic novel
Germany	2	9	2	2	5	-	4	1	Stage shows; Games; Art; Communication training; Networking platform; Videos/films
Greece	2	4	1	1	5	5	6	2	Education modules; Guided tours; Demonstration laboratories
Portugal	1	3	-	-	3	6	5	1	Digital games & art; Illustrations; Graphics, posters, flyers; digital games; Letter exchanges & meetings - scientists and children; Reports
Spain	4	5	3	3	2	6	5	1	Satisfaction surveys; Posters; Newsletters; Artistic performances; Illustrations; Protocols; Press releases; Art exhibitions
UK	4	5	5	3	5	2	7	3	-
TOTAL	20	45	14	14	26	24	47	9	-

Table 4: Main communication channels used by science communicators (n=78)

Country	Traditional media			Internet-based			Social media (interactive)							Selected others
	<i>TV</i>	<i>Radio</i>	<i>Newspaper</i>	<i>Websites</i>	<i>Blogs</i>	<i>Newsletters</i>	<i>LinkedIn</i>	<i>YouTube</i>	<i>Twitter</i>	<i>Instagram</i>	<i>TikTok</i>	<i>Facebook</i>	<i>Other SN</i>	
Denmark	3	3	6	5	6	1	2	-	-	2	-	1	5	Museum exhibits; Education programs for children
France	2	1	5	11	3	3	3	4	10	1	-	1	1	-
Germany	-	3	4	7	3	3	4	2	4	5	1	-	5	Artistic performance; podcast platforms; live events
Greece	1	1	5	10	1	-	1	5	2	3	3	3	3	Museum exhibits; live events
Portugal	2	1	4	10	1	4	4	2	3	7	1	3	6	Art installations; Live events; Letter exchanges
Spain	5	6	6	5	3	3	6	6	8	7	2	-	3	Webinars; live events
UK	6	5	8	8	7	5	4	4	8	2	1	-	1	WhatsApp; Telegram
TOTAL	19	20	38	56	24	19	24	23	35	27	8	8	24	-

Table 5: Audiences for science communicators' work

Country	Audiences
Denmark	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General public • Professional groups • School children
France	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General public • Readers of national press in print or online • Citizens unfamiliar with scientific culture, particularly teenagers and young adults • Science-related professional groups
Germany	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General public • Younger people interested in science, climate • Stakeholders in policy, industry, research • Journalism professional community
Greece	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adult and younger audiences with interest in science • Specialist audiences for medical, archaeology topics • Researchers and university students
Portugal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General public • Students and teachers at various educational levels • Specialist medical and rural audiences
Spain	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General public • Young people and students, educational • Citizens interested in climate change activism
UK	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General public • Citizens interested in Climate change, education and activism

Table 5 summarises the main audiences that communicators' work is targeted toward. The general public is the primary audience overall, with students and young people and citizens interested in climate change also prominently featured.

A particular focus of the project was science communicators working outside public institutions in private media companies, as freelancers, or internet-based popularizers of science-based content (both supportive and critical). A total of 52 interviews were conducted with these non-institutional communicators, evenly distributed across the seven countries. A further 26 interviews were conducted with institutional communicators, mainly working in research performing or publishing institutions, again evenly distributed by country.

2.2. Data analysis

Three identifier codes were assigned to the 78 interview transcript files: country (DE, DK, ES, FR, GR, PT, UK), type of interviewee (M, for Mediator) and the number of the interview (e.g. PT_M01). The transcripts were initially analysed by national teams using a codebook prepared

by the expert interviews project leaders (CSIC, Spain), in order to prepare National Reports (Woolley & Monsonís-Payá, 2024). In a second phase, the transcripts are being analysed by the Spanish team of researchers to respond to the research question presented in this paper. For this purpose, a second codebook has been designed and is being validated by a team of three researchers, who are coding the 78 transcripts using Nvivo Software.

4. Preliminary results: Translating research ethics and integrity (REI)

This section reports on the initial analysis of whether research integrity in scientific work and adherence to ethics standards and procedures has a positive effect on public trust. The study interviews tested this assumption by asking journalists, press officers, and other science communicators, about the sources of information they use in their work and how they assess the credibility of the information they use in producing their outputs. Formal markers of REI such as approvals by Ethics Committees were not important to participants, whether working in institutional roles close to science, in the media field, or as freelance popularizers of science.

Rather, science communicators assessed credibility through their professional practices and engagements. Non-institutional communicators are, in general, very comfortable dealing directly with scientific literature and do not rely on press releases from universities or publishers. They understand scientific journal hierarchies, and how these confer reputation-based credibility on information they may be considering translating into content for their audiences. However, the reliability of this information is not accepted unquestioningly based on journal or university reputations.

Institutional communicators speak directly with researchers and follow internal organisational protocols to assure themselves of the credibility of information about a new scientific result.

I think our role is to ask, and when we don't understand or when we find it strange to talk to others in the area. (...) I ask [researchers] in the specialty area, right? "Look, is this article really like that or, or do you think it's too much?" And when we have researchers who tell us, "Maybe these adjectives are a little too much", we have to do the down grading. (PT_M02)

(...) when there is a research result to promote and publicise, there is a process that is the same for everyone. There has to be scientific validation by the Institute. And scientific validation means that (...) for example for a result in [...], we go and see the deputy scientific director in charge of [...], we say "Oh, we've received this result, what do you think of it? Do we publicise it or not?" So, whether the results come to us from the delegation, from the communication office, or from the lab, the process is the same, it'll be the same ... no one will work individually I think. (FR_M09)

Although a research result may have already passed a process of peer review within the scientific community, institutional communicators engage in a process of consultation and verification to satisfy themselves that scientific work merits dissemination and promotion.

Non-institutional science communicators also require more than prestige as a safeguard that the information they are considering using is credible.

So, it is definitely not enough to quote someone just because they have a title; you have to check if they can speak credibly, if it aligns with the rest of the research. So, it's important for me to be able to assess that. (DE_M03)

The issue of consensus is something that's often an important point when approaching a topic (...) When I work in a team, if we know that we have something to talk about, if we know that (...) scientists are more or less all in agreement, we'll start with that topic. That doesn't mean that you can't mention opposing views, and it doesn't mean that you can't mention certain things that are still being developed or on which there is no consensus, if that's not the focus of the topic. (FR_M11)

Great store is placed on understanding the state-of-the-art in a particular topic or discipline. The relationship of a particular finding or paper to the scientific consensus is important and something communicators feel they must personally understand.

The importance of interpersonal connections in building confidence and receiving assurance is also evident.

It's often difficult to get answers to these questions from press releases from universities. You don't usually get them from papers either. You're most likely to get them if you have researchers on the phone. (DE_M03)

As I only deal there with a very closed group of scientists, I already know that they are, at least initially, credible... (PT_M04)

It is important to me that the people I use as sources have standards of scientific integrity, and I try to determine that based on various criteria. Naturally, when I talk to experts, I don't initially discuss their integrity standards but try to determine it by other factors. (DE_M10)

Professional science journalists are particularly conscientious about the credibility and reliability of their sources. Many specialist science journalists work for large media organisations, where fact-checking and the veracity of their contributions are essential. Their training in professional standards is a first line of assurance when dealing with novel or potentially attention-grabbing science information.

Once you are trained, you know by the book how the professional evaluation of research quality goes. And for that, you need to be a science journalist; you can't be anything else. That is the internal distinction we have, which is somewhat threatened by the sheer quantity of online content. (DE_M08)

Science journalists also place a high value on the scientific consensus. The apparent novelty of results does not guarantee its take-up.

I must be able to reflect on the state of research. I cannot pretend that a single result fell from the sky and that nothing was known before. That is a common journalistic mistake, seeing paradigm shifts everywhere when there are none. When 50 papers make a statement and one says something different, it is still 50 to one. (DE_M08)

But perhaps even more important for specialist science journalists is to engage in a process of third-party verification or assessment of new information that they may wish to develop into new content.

The evaluation is done firstly indirectly through the fact that they have gone through a peer review process etc. And secondly, to the extent that they are in subjects in which I have a relative competence, I can also have a relative judgment. The second is in relevant material with which I come into contact through my network of associates, either at the university or former professional

associates, with whatever credibility they can offer to the material proposed by them, with positive or negative connotations. And the third one, on the websites that I mostly trust, is a matter of whether they have proper citations to reliable sources or whether the very writing of their writers is trustworthy. (GR_M04)

So that's probably one of the most complicated parts of the job (...) It's really difficult. First of all, because people change... those who are serious can become not so serious, they can start talking nonsense about a subject... It's a constant job to get colleagues to reaffirm the seriousness of this or that person. I work like this a lot (...) I'll give you an example: a scientific study that we think is great. We want to talk about it. We'll call the researchers, the team, etc., and then (...) if we have time, we'll try to force ourselves to always call outside people we know, who have a good reputation, and say to them: "Oh, have you seen this? Is this interesting research?" (...) Of course we have to try to do some research. For researchers, we check the Retraction Watch database to see if they've had any articles retracted (...). (FR_M07)

Journalists with large daily newspapers sometimes receive privileged or advance notice of new articles that publishers or institutions wish to promote.

I have several sources of experts in scientific ethics, so we send them the paper, as we have access to the papers under embargo, a few days before publication we have 5 or 6 days to send it to experts in ethics and they tell us, "I don't see any problem in making an embryo with a mixture of human and monkey cells", or if this is controversial as it is ethics... (ES_M11)

Rather than rely on their own experience or knowledge of the scientist or institution producing new results, journalists also use the services of specialists, including in ethics, to assist them form confidence in scientific results as a basis for their work.

Science journalists thus use multiple sources of verification in order to gain an overall picture of the research they are assessing. This includes a dual assessment of the research results themselves but also of the scientist or research group that has produced the result. This is not a static landscape, and reputations are not eternal or universal. External validation needs to be updated and past experience alone cannot be assumed to guarantee credibility.

To conclude, science communicators assess the credibility of scientific information by a mix of reputational, interpersonal, and professional elements. They perceive their own socially embedded practices and field experience as the basis for a process of selecting credible information that itself contributes to driving integrity in research. They do not rely on, or promote in their outputs, the formal ethics processes and integrity practices institutionalised in scientific work. It thus appears that adherence to formal processes of REI in scientific knowledge production and institutions does not have a direct or significant impact on levels of public trust in science. In terms of the roles of science communicators in mediating between knowledge production processes and citizens they appear to engage in a socio-technical 'quality assurance' analytics that combines knowledge, expertise, social capital and field experience with a 'public good' orientation. It may be that understanding communicators' roles in such a way can be helpful in future efforts to interrogate the objectives, relational structure, and effectiveness of its inverse manifestation as science-focused mis- and disinformation.

Open science practices

An open research protocol for the study reported here was published on Zenodo prior to the start of data collection (Monsonís-Payá & Woolley 2024). There is no plan to make interview transcripts available due to participants' rights to privacy and anonymity.

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Author contributions

Irene Monsonís-Payá and Richard Woolley contributed equally to the preparation of this paper.

Competing interests

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